

SEPSIS AND SEPTIC SHOCK IN INFANTS AND CHILDREN: MICROBIOLOGICAL FEATURES AND TREATMENT STRATEGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16745265>

Abstract. *Pediatric sepsis remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality in intensive care units. Early diagnosis and assessment of the severity of septic conditions play a key role in optimizing antimicrobial strategies and reducing lethality. This review summarizes findings from meta-analyses on severe bacterial infections and sepsis in pediatric patients, as well as the Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC) recommendations of 2020 and 2021. The 2020 SSC pediatric guidelines did not identify strong evidence or sufficient data to support firm recommendations regarding antimicrobial therapy in children and neonates with sepsis or septic shock.*

Over the past decade, several small and large studies have been published in pediatrics with suggested approaches to antimicrobial therapy. However, due to the heterogeneity of pediatric ICUs in terms of patient age, disease profile, severity, comorbidities, and the variability of local microbial landscapes, it is unreasonable to expect a single antimicrobial strategy to suit all septic patients. Therefore, most clinicians emphasize the need for an individualized approach to antimicrobial therapy in children, taking into account the infection source, disease severity, microbial environment, and immune status.

Keywords: *pediatric sepsis, neonatal sepsis, prognostic criteria, antimicrobial strategy, intensive care, biomarkers, targeted antimicrobial therapy.*

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global incidence of pediatric sepsis and septic shock is estimated to be approximately 4.2 million cases annually, with 3 million occurring in neonates and infants—equivalent to 9.7 cases per 1,000 children [1]. The highest case fatality rates are observed in children with endocarditis and central nervous system (CNS) infections—16.7% and 15.2%, respectively. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is one of the major contributors to sepsis-related mortality, accounting for over 700,000 deaths annually, exacerbated by the slow pace of new antibiotic development.

The rising incidence of sepsis in children reflects a broader global trend. Numerous international studies have demonstrated that mortality from sepsis can be reduced only through the very early initiation of targeted and comprehensive treatment. Successful outcomes depend on unified diagnostic approaches, adherence to internationally recognized criteria, and early identification of sepsis.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Sepsis-3 international classification has yet to be fully implemented nationwide. Consequently, the diagnosis of “sepsis” is often made at later stages of illness. Antibacterial therapy (ABT), when combined with appropriate source control, is a critical determinant of outcomes in intensive care settings. Recent studies emphasize the importance of dynamic monitoring and the adaptation of antimicrobial strategies based on prognostic indicators to improve patient outcomes.

Literature Search Strategy

To identify relevant publications evaluating the adequacy of antimicrobial therapy in children and neonates with sepsis, a literature search was conducted using the keywords “*sepsis in children*,” “*antibiotic therapy*,” and “*critical conditions*.” The search covered the past 10–15 years and included databases such as the Russian Scientific Electronic Library (elibrary.ru), PubMed, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect. A limited number of studies focusing specifically on pediatric sepsis were identified, with the exception of those addressing neonatal sepsis. The review includes analysis of pediatric guidelines on sepsis and septic shock from the Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC-2020), as well as clinical studies referenced in the SSC-2021 antimicrobial therapy guidance.

Results

The antimicrobial therapy (AMT) strategies for pediatric and neonatal sepsis and septic shock have been thoroughly described in several multicenter reviews [2,3]. Neonates and infants, hospitalized patients, and children with autoimmune disorders represent the most vulnerable populations at risk of developing sepsis [4]. Bacterial pathogens are responsible for more than 95% of sepsis and septic shock cases. The etiological structure of sepsis varies depending on the patient’s age. In infancy, the most common causative agents are *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Neisseria meningitidis*. Among Gram-positive organisms, streptococci, staphylococci, and enterococci are predominant. In recent decades, there has been a notable rise in methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and an increasing incidence of infections caused by conditionally pathogenic *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.

The detection rate of bacteremia in patients with sepsis ranges from 20% to 75%, due to various factors such as the anatomical distance of the infection focus from the bloodstream, improper blood culture collection techniques, or prior administration of antibiotics before sampling. Blood culture remains the most commonly used method for detecting bacteremia. Pathogen identification in blood has crucial implications for selecting the appropriate type and duration of AMT and is essential for identifying multidrug-resistant organisms [5].

Early blood culture collection is recommended before initiating AMT in children with sepsis or septic shock. Several observational studies have shown that a comprehensive initial resuscitation approach—including early blood culture collection—is associated with improved outcomes [2,6]. The collection of other biological specimens (e.g., urine, cerebrospinal fluid, tracheal aspirate, bronchoalveolar lavage) should also be performed as early as possible. Depending on the suspected site of infection, these samples may offer a higher diagnostic yield than blood cultures. Clinicians should also consider age-, sex-, and comorbidity-specific epidemiological patterns of pediatric infections [3,7]. A recent large-scale population-based study [3] found that approximately one in three episodes of bacteremia was associated with organ dysfunction.

Standard blood culture methods have several limitations, including the time required for microbial growth and identification, assessment of antibiotic susceptibility, and the impact of prior antibiotic administration on diagnostic yield. Emerging molecular diagnostic technologies now offer faster and more accurate microbial identification, often detecting pathogens well before blood cultures turn positive [2]. Furthermore, randomized controlled trials (RCTs) have identified other important secondary endpoints linked to earlier antibiotic initiation, including reduced overall length of stay and shorter durations of organ dysfunction (OD) [9,10].

Thus, timely initiation of antimicrobial therapy (AMT), ideally as part of a comprehensive initial management bundle, should be a primary goal in children with septic shock. However, the definition of “timely” remains a subject of ongoing debate, as it is closely tied to challenges in the precise diagnosis of sepsis or septic shock, and the need to balance treatment timing against quality-of-life considerations, such as the avoidance of unnecessary antibiotic use [11].

One pediatric randomized controlled trial (RCT) demonstrated a dose-response gradient: the longer the delay in initiating AMT, the higher the mortality rate. A second, larger study found a significant reduction in mortality when antimicrobial agents were administered within one hour—but only as part of a broader bundle including blood cultures and fluid resuscitation [2]. Available pediatric data do not define a strict time threshold beyond which mortality risk increases, but suggest that the potential for harm escalates as delays in AMT lengthen—particularly beyond the three-hour mark. The greatest survival benefit for initiating AMT within the first hour was observed in cohorts dominated by septic shock [2].

In children without overt signs of shock, the diagnosis of sepsis-induced organ dysfunction (OD) is more complex, often requiring clinicians to distinguish true sepsis from suspected infection without systemic compromise [8]. Based on the above evidence, it is recommended that AMT be initiated as early as possible following the recognition of sepsis. However, in patients without clinical signs of shock, up to three hours may be used for appropriate diagnostic workup. In contrast, once septic shock is confirmed, AMT should be administered immediately.

Mortality in pediatric sepsis is strongly associated with delays in initiating appropriate AMT, underscoring the importance of prompt and accurate antibiotic selection [12,13].

“Empirical therapy” refers to the initial choice of antimicrobial agents prior to microbiological confirmation of the causative pathogen (see Table 1). This approach is based on the predicted likelihood of bacterial etiologies. Empirical AMT should provide broad-spectrum coverage for the most probable pathogens, recognizing that rare organisms may still fall outside of coverage. “Broad-spectrum therapy” involves using single or combination agents with activity against multiple classes of bacteria or pathogens. Such regimens are recommended for the initial empirical treatment of children with septic shock or sepsis-induced organ dysfunction, in order to maximize the likelihood of therapeutic success.

The initial selection of empirical antimicrobial therapy (AMT) should take into account a patient’s clinical history, including age, suspected site of infection, comorbidities, and the presence of indwelling medical devices. Patients with recent or ongoing healthcare exposure should receive empirical treatment that reflects potential colonization with healthcare-associated pathogens as well as any recent antibiotic use [3].

Sepsis in children and neonates is most commonly caused by Gram-negative or Gram-positive bacteria, although the relative prevalence of each varies by age, geographic region, and whether the infection is community- or hospital-acquired. Invasive fungal infections are typically limited to immunocompromised or preterm neonates. Neutropenic patients are at increased risk for infections caused by a broad spectrum of pathogens, including multidrug-resistant Gram-negative bacilli and *Candida* species. Neonates are also at risk for sepsis due to *Listeria monocytogenes* and disseminated herpes simplex virus infection.

Children with chronic illnesses who are receiving inpatient care are more likely to develop sepsis caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE). In patients at high risk of infection with

multidrug-resistant organisms, broad-spectrum empirical AMT regimens may require the use of multiple agents to ensure adequate coverage of likely pathogens.

Table 1.

Definitions of Empirical, Targeted/Definitive, Broad-Spectrum, and Multidrug Antimicrobial Therapy

Definition	Timing	Commentary
Empirical AMT	Initial AMT initiated based on suspected infection in the absence of definitive microbiological identification of the pathogen.	Empirical therapy may consist of one or multiple agents but must provide broad-spectrum coverage. It should be based on local, regional, or national epidemiological data and patient-specific risk factors.
Targeted AMT	AMT directed at specific pathogen(s), usually after microbiological identification.	Targeted (definitive) therapy may consist of one or more agents but should not be broader than necessary for treatment of the identified pathogen(s) based on microbiological results.
Broad-Spectrum AMT	Antimicrobial regimen with activity against multiple groups of bacteria and/or other pathogens considered likely causes of the clinical syndrome.	Broad-spectrum AMT may consist of a single agent or multiple agents.
Combination AMT	More than one antibiotic is required to: (1) expand the antimicrobial spectrum to include additional potential pathogens (e.g., vancomycin for MRSA); (2) reduce the risk of resistance to any single agent (e.g., in patients with known colonization or infection with multidrug-resistant organisms); or (3) achieve synergy against a suspected or confirmed pathogen.	Combination therapy is used to enhance coverage, prevent resistance, or improve efficacy through synergistic action. This approach is common in critically ill or immunocompromised patients.

For previously healthy children with community-acquired sepsis, third-generation cephalosporins (e.g., ceftriaxone) may be sufficient as empirical therapy. Vancomycin should be added in settings where pneumococcal strains resistant to MRSA or ceftriaxone are prevalent. The addition of aminoglycosides or substitution with a carbapenem is warranted in regions with high rates of ceftriaxone-resistant Gram-negative organisms.

For immunocompromised patients or those with healthcare-associated sepsis, empirical antimicrobial therapy should be initiated with advanced-generation antipseudomonal cephalosporins (e.g., cefepime), broad-spectrum carbapenems (e.g., meropenem,

imipenem/cilastatin), or extended-spectrum penicillin/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations (e.g., piperacillin/tazobactam) [14].

In neonates, antimicrobial regimens should include ampicillin to cover *Listeria monocytogenes*, along with empirical acyclovir if there is clinical suspicion of herpes simplex virus (HSV) infection. In patients with suspected or confirmed intra-abdominal sources of infection, therapy should ensure adequate coverage of gastrointestinal pathogens, including anaerobes—either through a combination of extended-spectrum penicillin/ β -lactamase inhibitors or carbapenems, or by adding clindamycin or metronidazole.

In cases of sepsis complicated by influenza-like illness during influenza season, empirical antiviral therapy should be initiated pending respiratory virus test results [15,16]. Patients at high risk for antibiotic-resistant infections due to prior colonization, local epidemiology, or recent antimicrobial exposure should receive an individualized empirical antimicrobial regimen.

In suspected cases of toxic shock syndrome or necrotizing fasciitis, empirical therapy should include clindamycin or lincomycin to inhibit toxin production and enhance bacterial clearance [17].

“Targeted” or “definitive” therapy refers to an antimicrobial regimen directed at a specific pathogen after microbiological identification. Similar to empirical therapy, targeted therapy may involve one or more agents, but its spectrum should not exceed what is necessary for the treatment of the identified microorganism [18].

Continuing broad-spectrum AMT unnecessarily poses significant risks, including direct toxicities such as nephrotoxicity or ototoxicity (e.g., with aminoglycosides), infections caused by *Clostridioides difficile* or fungal pathogens, and the promotion of antimicrobial resistance both in individual patients and within the community. Furthermore, excessive antibiotic exposure may disrupt the developing human microbiome in early life—a phenomenon not yet fully understood but increasingly associated with adverse outcomes, such as necrotizing enterocolitis in neonates.

Since most bacterial cultures show significant growth within 24–36 hours when a pathogen is present [19], empirical AMT should be reassessed no later than 48 hours after initiation. If no pathogen is identified and bacterial or fungal infection is deemed unlikely, clinicians should consider discontinuing empirical antimicrobial agents to avoid unnecessary exposure.

However, in many children with a clinical diagnosis of septic shock, no pathogen is isolated [20]. Negative microbiological results may be falsely reassuring due to prior antibiotic therapy, absence of bacteremia, or the presence of sepsis driven by viral infections.

Therefore, decisions regarding the continuation, narrowing, or discontinuation of AMT must often be guided by clinical judgment and indirect indicators—such as the patient’s overall clinical picture, anatomical site and type of infection, risk factors, and the adequacy of clinical improvement [21].

Empirical antimicrobial therapy (AMT) may be either monotherapy or combination therapy, but should always provide broad-spectrum coverage, as described in Table 1. In certain clinical scenarios—or when specific types of infection are suspected—it may be necessary to add a glycopeptide agent (e.g., vancomycin) to ensure coverage of MRSA, or to include a second Gram-negative agent (e.g., an aminoglycoside in addition to a beta-lactam or a second/third-generation cephalosporin) when there is a high risk of antimicrobial resistance.

However, routine inclusion of aminoglycosides or glycopeptides for the purposes of synergy or “dual coverage” in empirical regimens is not supported by current evidence [22,23].

A recent Cochrane review evaluated beta-lactam monotherapy versus combination therapy with beta-lactams and aminoglycosides for sepsis, including 69 trials with a total of 7,863 participants, both neonates and children [21]. In studies where both groups received the same beta-lactam, no significant differences in clinical outcomes were observed. In trials where the monotherapy group received a beta-lactam with broader-spectrum activity than the combination group, monotherapy showed a possible mortality benefit (OR 0.85; 95% CI 0.71–1.01) and a significant advantage in clinical failure rates (OR 0.75; 95% CI 0.67–0.84) [21].

Therefore, many children with septic shock or sepsis-related organ dysfunction do not require empiric multidrug therapy [21].

Nonetheless, in selected clinical scenarios, multidrug regimens may be appropriate. For example, in patients at high risk for drug-resistant Gram-negative infections, a combination of beta-lactam/beta-lactamase inhibitors (e.g., piperacillin/tazobactam) with aminoglycosides (e.g., gentamicin) may be used to extend coverage against both susceptible and resistant organisms, until definitive identification and susceptibility data are available [24,25].

Moreover, synergistic multidrug regimens may be warranted even in definitive therapy for certain conditions—such as device-related infections, enterococcal endocarditis, staphylococcal endocarditis, group B streptococcal sepsis, and infections caused by carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* [26].

Pediatric oncology patients and hematopoietic stem cell transplant (HSCT) recipients experience profound immunosuppression and represent a high-risk population for colonization and infection with multidrug-resistant organisms (MDROs) [27]. According to the 2017 guidelines for the management of fever and neutropenia in pediatric cancer patients and HSCT recipients, monotherapy with an anti-pseudomonal beta-lactam, a fourth-generation cephalosporin, or a carbapenem is recommended as empirical treatment in high-risk settings [14].

Randomized controlled trials in children comparing beta-lactam monotherapy to combination therapy with aminoglycosides found no significant differences in treatment failure, infection-related mortality, or overall mortality [14]. A meta-analysis also confirmed the efficacy and safety of monotherapy without the addition of aminoglycosides. However, the 2017 guidelines recommend adding a second Gram-negative agent and/or a glycopeptide when resistant organisms are suspected in patients with clinical instability (e.g., septic shock) or in healthcare settings with high local resistance rates [14].

Given current sepsis and septic shock incidence and mortality rates, a local or regional resistance rate exceeding 10% is likely a reasonable threshold for the empirical addition of a second agent targeting the suspected pathogen [20].

Sepsis may significantly alter the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of antimicrobial agents. Therefore, antimicrobial dosing should be individualized to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy. Subtherapeutic dosing may result in treatment failure, prolonged organ dysfunction, and the development of antimicrobial resistance.

Many patients with sepsis are at risk of altered drug metabolism and/or clearance—especially those with renal or hepatic dysfunction or those receiving extracorporeal therapies [28]. In particular, continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) can significantly modify antimicrobial clearance, necessitating dose adjustments [29,30]. Hepatic dysfunction may impair the metabolism of lipophilic and highly protein-bound antibiotics, increasing the risk of drug accumulation and toxicity. In renal

dysfunction, time-dependent antibiotics such as beta-lactams often require reduced dosing frequency to prevent accumulation.

The inappropriate and excessive use of broad-spectrum antimicrobials in healthcare, community settings, veterinary medicine, and the environment has contributed to the emergence of a global public health emergency related to antimicrobial resistance (AMR). To date, quality improvement (QI) initiatives in adult populations have demonstrated that safe and effective antimicrobial de-escalation can be achieved through daily reassessment and structured discussions [31]. In neonates, shortening the duration of antimicrobial therapy has also been shown to be safe when guided by procalcitonin levels.

Although the direct relationship between antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) and reduced antimicrobial resistance has not yet been conclusively established, existing evidence suggests that ASPs in inpatient pediatric settings can successfully reduce antimicrobial use without compromising clinical outcomes.

The “Start Smart – Then Focus” initiative from Public Health England outlines a pragmatic five-point strategy for antimicrobial prescribing decisions:

1. stop antimicrobials if there is no evidence of infection,
2. switch from intravenous to oral therapy when appropriate,
3. change the antimicrobial—ideally to a narrower spectrum agent, or to a broader one if required,
4. continue treatment but document the next review or stop date, and
5. consider outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy (OPAT) when feasible [32].

The primary goals of antimicrobial therapy in patients with sepsis are the rapid reduction of pathogen burden and the prevention of recurrence. The optimal duration of therapy varies depending on the infection site due to factors such as the diversity of pathogens, poor drug penetration into certain tissues, or the presence of biofilms that are difficult to eradicate.

For example, longer treatment durations are typically required for endocarditis, undrained abscesses, and prosthetic joint infections when the device cannot be removed. The optimal course of treatment for endocarditis caused by methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) may be shorter than for methicillin-resistant strains (MRSA). Similarly, while 7–10 days of therapy may be appropriate for uncomplicated Gram-negative bacteremia in immunocompetent hosts [33], uncomplicated bacteremia caused by *S. aureus* usually necessitates longer treatment, likely due to undetected foci of infection [34].

A recent systematic review assessed studies evaluating the duration of treatment for microbiologically confirmed infections in children and provided evidence-based clinical recommendations on the optimal length of antimicrobial therapy for specific conditions. Observational data suggest that prolonged antibiotic exposure may increase the risk of adverse outcomes, including necrotizing enterocolitis in preterm neonates [35], candidemia in hospitalized children [70], development of antimicrobial resistance, and *Clostridioides difficile* infections.

Several meta-analyses, randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and observational studies have compared short- and long-course antibiotic regimens for serious infections [36,37,38]. The majority of these studies suggest that shorter courses are associated with clinical outcomes comparable to those of extended courses. This applies to conditions such as neonatal bacteremia [38], pyelonephritis, and uncomplicated bacterial meningitis [37].

The role of source control in pediatric sepsis is less well studied. However, its importance has been demonstrated in cases involving skin and soft tissue abscesses and necrotizing fasciitis

[39]. One of the most common sources of infection in this population is central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSIs). Delayed removal of central venous catheters (CVCs) in neonates, and in patients with fungemia or *Enterobacteriaceae* bacteremia, has been shown to increase the risk of death or delay recovery [40].

Conclusion

Blood culture remains the gold standard for diagnosing sepsis. However, the absence of bacteremia does not rule out the diagnosis when clinical and laboratory criteria for sepsis are present. For bacteriological confirmation, a single positive culture is sufficient if pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (including MRSA), *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, or fungi are isolated.

Timely administration of antimicrobial therapy (ideally within 1 hour of diagnosis) should be the primary goal in children with septic shock. In all cases of suspected sepsis, antibiotic therapy should be initiated as early as possible, allowing up to 3 hours for diagnostic evaluation in patients without clinical signs of shock.

The decision to continue, narrow, or discontinue antimicrobial therapy should be based on clinician judgment and indirect clinical indicators, taking into account the clinical presentation, site and type of infection, individual risk factors, and adequacy of clinical improvement.

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